

NCAS Computing Skills Training

Introduction to Scientific Computing

bit.ly/ncasIntroSciComp

The Introduction to Scientific Computing (ISC) course covers the skills needed for managing and analysing data using Linux and Python. The training is suitable for those without experience as well as those looking to improve or refresh their computing skills. The course consists of presentations and practical exercises to give hands-on experience of:

- An introduction to the Linux shell
- An introduction to programming in Python
- Python for data analysis: arrays and visualisation
- Reading instrument data and working with netCDF files
- Version control systems and working with online repositories

NCAS Data Tools

The *cf-python* and *cf-plot* Python packages build on the CF metadata conventions to provide powerful extraction, regridding and visualization capabilities of netCDF, Met Office PP and fields files. Operations such as reading, grid transformation and plotting of contours and vectors can be performed in a single line of code making for quick analysis and plotting of data. This is a one day course and also introduces the Jupyter Notebook Python programming environment.

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